

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF - CONTROL AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The present investigation is a modest attempt to study the relationship between self-control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students. Normative survey method was employed for the investigation and a sample of 300 higher secondary students studying in Cuddalore district were selected by using the simple random sampling method. Self-control Inventory (SCI) Constructed and standardized by Singh AK and Sengupta A (1996) and Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) constructed and standardized by Singh PY and Bharagava M (1990) were used to collect the necessary data. The collected data was analyzed by using required statistical techniques. The results of the study revealed that higher secondary students have high self-control and high emotional maturity. Moreover, it was found that there exists a positive and a significant relationship between self-control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students.

Introduction:

Education is the process by which people acquire knowledge, skills, habits, values and attitudes. It necessarily helps people to become useful members of the society. It develops an appreciation of one's cultural heritage. Both parents and teachers help the learners to develop right attitudes, habits and values that help modify their character and remain with them throughout life. According to Concise Oxford Dictionary, the word education means the process of educating or being educated or the theory and practice of teaching. In the words of A. S. Altekar (1958), "Education has always been regarded in India as a source of illumination and power which transforms and ennobles our nature by the progressive and harmonious development of our physical, mental, intellectual and spiritual powers and faculties."

Higher Secondary Education:

The Indian Education Commission (Kothari Commission) (1964-66) recommended educational reconstruction by introducing a broadly uniform pattern of 10+2+3 throughout the country. It is the deciding stage for students because at this stage one attains the mental growth that enables one to decide one's future. Students begin to understand the diverse cultural and social system of the people living in different parts of the country. It also promotes equality, neighborhood, brotherhood and unity. Adequate arrangements will be made to give vocational training to the disabled.

Meaning and Definition of Self-Control:

Self – Control is one of the important but relatively ignored dimensions of personality. According to Berk (1972) self-control we mean ability to inhibit the expression of spontaneous impulses. According to Mischel (1979) when the delay is self imposed it is known as self-control. Self – control refers to behavior in which a person monitors his or her own actions in absence of or in contradiction to the pressures in the immediate environment.

Characteristics of Self-Control:

A well adjusted person has some insights into understand his motives, desires, his sickness and strong points. He can evaluate his behavior objectively and can accept his shortcomings; he has a sense of personal worth, feel worthwhile and important. He has self – respect and feels secure in the group. He has faith in his ability to succeed. He has the sense of personal security. He feels confident of himself in his everyday life more or less effectively. He develops a capacity to tolerate frustration and disappointment in his daily life.

Meaning and Definition of Emotional Maturity:

Emotional maturity refers to your ability to understand, and manage, your emotions. Emotional maturity enables you to create the life you desire. A life filled with happiness and fulfilment. You define success in your own terms, not society's and you strive to achieve it.

Concept of Emotional Maturity:

In the developmental concept, maturity is that state of personality reached at any particular stage of development when the inherent growth pattern has not been subject to environmental warping. Mental health reflects a dynamic equilibrium between a relatively mature individual and his environment. The goal toward which emotional development tends is the basic, constructive, responsible, giving attitude of the parent to the wanted, loved child. "Emotional maturity has been well termed the master concept of our time."

Need for the Study:

In general, students differ in their self-control as well as in their field of confidence and in interest. Though the teachers provide the same type of instruction to all students in the class room, some of them are very high and some of them are very low in their characters and the ability of facing the problem. The parents and teachers expect their children to do better as they provide all facilities they can in and outside their house. Therefore, present study considering the characteristics of the self control person. The investigator felt the need to study the self-control of the student and emotional maturity

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the present study.

- To find out the level of higher secondary school students self control.
- To find out the level of higher secondary school students Emotional Maturity.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between self-control and emotional maturity.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- The Level of self control among higher secondary students is average.
- The Level of emotional maturity among higher secondary students is average.
- There is no significance relationship between self control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students.

Method and Sample of the Study:

In the present study normative survey method is adopted. In the present study, the investigator has adopted simple random sampling technique for selecting the sample from the population. The sample consists of 300 higher secondary students from schools in Cuddalore District of Tamil Nadu.

Tools Used:

- Self-Control Inventory (SCI), Constructed and standardized by Singh AK and Sengupta A (1996).
- Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) constructed and standardized by Singh P.Y and Bharagava M (1990).

Statistical Analysis of the Data and Interpretation:

Ho₁ : The Level of self control among higher secondary students is average.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Self-Control of Higher Secondary Students

Variable	No. of Students	Mean	SD
Self-Control	300	16.74	7.90

It is evident from the table 4.1 the computed mean and standard deviation values of self-control of the higher secondary students on total self-control are found to be 16.74 and 7.90 respectively, which indicates that the mean and standard scores of the total sample is above the mid score of 15. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that the self-control of higher secondary student is high.

Ho₂ : The Level of emotional maturity among higher secondary students is average.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students

Variable	No. of Students	Mean	SD
Emotional Maturity	300	123.27	27.17

It is evident from the table 4.2 the computed mean and standard deviation values of emotional maturity of the higher secondary school students on total emotional maturity are found to be 123.27 and 27.17 respectively, which indicates that the mean and standard scores of the total sample is above the mid score of 120. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that higher secondary students are having high level of emotional maturity.

Ho₃ : There is no significant relationship between Self-Control and Emotional Maturity of higher Secondary students.

Table 3: Relationship between Self-Control and Emotional Maturity of Higher Secondary Students

Variables	Numbers	Correlation Co-Efficient (r) Value	Level of Significance at 5% Level
Self-Control and Emotional Maturity	300	0.127	Significant

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'r' value is 0.127 which is higher than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result is that, there is significant relationship between Self Control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students.

Findings of the Study:

- The self-control of higher secondary student is high.
- The higher secondary students are having high level of emotional maturity.
- There is significant relationship between Self Control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students.

Conclusion:

The present study the relationship between self-control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students. Findings revealed that higher secondary students have high self-control and high emotional maturity. Moreover, it was found that there exists a positive and a significant relationship between self-control and emotional maturity of higher secondary students.

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